

Research article

A further study of kinship terms for ‘mother’ in Vietnamese

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Abstract: This paper offers a comprehensive look at kinship terms in Vietnamese, highlighting the specific case of kinship terms for ‘mother.’ The terms for ‘mother’ are abundant in the Vietnamese kinship term system and include terms that are used nationwide as well as those that have been preserved in dialects. Among them are some cases which seem to have sufficient historical phonetic evidence to argue about their origin. Meanwhile, the origin of other terms for ‘mother’ is still under debate. Based on historical linguistic evidence supported by the interpretation of linguistics maps, this paper aims to give more insight into the origin and development of four Vietnamese kinship terms for ‘mother’: *mẹ*, *mê*, *mạ*, *má*. The findings indicate that there are terms for ‘mother’ that are Austroasiatic etymons (*mẹ*, *mạ*, *mê*), while *má* is likely to be a loanword from Chinese dialects.

Keywords: kinship term; mother; Vietnamese; historical linguistics; geolinguistics

1. Introduction

The study of Vietnamese kinship terms has indeed captivated the attention of both Vietnamese and foreign linguists for a long time. These scholars have approached these terms from several perspectives, which has contributed to a deep understanding of Vietnamese language and culture. Previous studies by linguists have delved into structural and semantic aspects as well as the use of these terms as pronouns and terms of address in daily social communication.

In terms of historical perspective, the study by Mark Alves (2017) on Chinese loanwords in Vietnamese pronouns and terms of address and reference pointed out the source of some kinship terms, which has made a noteworthy contribution to this issue. According to his findings, a dozen kinship terms were borrowed from Chinese during an early period of Sino–Vietnamese contact and that this borrowing took place over multiple periods of Chinese historical phonology: *thím* (father’s younger brother’s

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wife), *mợ* (mother's younger brother's wife), *chú* (father's younger), *cậu* (mother's younger brother), *bác* (father or mother's elder sister/brother), *chị* (elder sister), *bà* (grandmother), *ông* (grandfather), *cô* (father's younger sister), *đì* (mother's younger sister). Their original semantic features were kept while developing anaphoric functions not seen in Chinese, with a distinction between kinship terms within families versus those used in society more generally. The study also revealed that the etymological source of some of the terms is Austroasiatic: *con*, *cháu*. However, the sources of some of the terms are still unknown: *cụ/cổ* (great-grandfather, very old person), *anh* (elder brother), *em* (younger sibling), *duyệt* (aunt's husband), *cha/bố/thầy* (father), *so* (great-grandparent). With regard to the term for 'mother,' Alves listed two cases, *mẹ* and *má*, but the source of these two terms was left open because as Alves noted, comparable forms of *mẹ* and *má* could be found in both Austroasiatic and Tai-Kadai languages.

In my research (Tran Thi Hong Hanh 2021), I discussed the origin of certain kinship terms in the Phú Thọ dialect (a Northern Vietnamese dialect) and indicated that the term *bằm* used to refer to 'mother' here is an Austroasiatic etymon. Based on historical phonetic correspondences, I argued that *bằm* has the etymological meaning of 'to suck, to breastfeed' and therefore, it was developed to designate a 'breastfeeding woman.' I also proposed that the process was likely the same with other terms referring to 'mother': *bu*, *vú*, *u*, *đẽ*. In another study of mine (Tran Thi Hong Hanh 2023), I also examined other kinship terms and gave my explanation of the source of *con* (child, offspring), *cháu* (grandchild), *chắt* (great-grandchild), *chít* (great-great-grandchild), *chít* (great-great-great-grandchild), some terms for 'mother' such as *me*, *mợ*, *mụ*, and some female kinship terms such as (bà) *vãi* (maternal grandmother), *ả* (sister), and *già* (aunt/ grandmother). However, my analysis differed from that of Alves in several respects. I was inclined to suggest that the source of *mẹ* (and *mạ*) was Austroasiatic, whereas *má* seemed to originate from Chinese dialects.

In reviewing the literature, I discovered that although a general consensus seems to exist regarding the source of certain kinship terms in Vietnamese, there are still differences of opinion and some weak arguments concerning this, which need further study. Thus, this paper continues the discussion of the origin of the kinship terms in Vietnamese, focusing on the origin analysis of some terms for 'mother.' By providing additional evidence on the geographical distribution of these terms, this paper is expected to contribute to identifying and clarifying their origin.

2. Data and discussion

There are various terms to refer to ‘mother’ among Vietnamese dialects. These terms can be divided into two groups: terms that are all open syllables starting with the first consonant /m/: *mẹ, me, mạ, mợ, mệ, mẹ, má,* and terms that do not have /m/ as first consonant: *bà, bu, u, vú, đẽ, cái, nạ.* Some of these terms specifically and primarily mean “mother”: *mẹ, me, mạ, má, bà, u,* while others have multiple meanings that refer to female relatives who are not necessarily mother. These include words such as *mụ, mệ,* and *mợ* or words that are used as nouns to refer to female breasts, verbs meaning ‘to give birth,’ or adjectives meaning ‘female,’ ‘king-sized,’ or ‘main.’ These data were collected from various sources such as dictionaries of idioms and proverbs and dialect dictionaries. Moreover, in order to draw the linguistic map, we conducted surveys and interviews with informants in different localities using questionnaires. The data related to the reconstructions of Mon-Khmer languages are all from the Mon-Khmer Etymological Dictionary (MKED) and reconstructions of Tai languages are cited from Li Fang Kuei (1977) and/or Pittayaporn (2009). Among the kinship terms for ‘mother,’ the terms *bà, bu, u, vú,* and *đẽ* were discussed in my previous studies (Trần Thị Hồng Hạnh 2021, 2023). Thus, this paper will focus on other terms.

2.1. The case of *mẹ, mệ, and mạ*

According to the MKED, Proto-Mon Khmer has four reconstructed forms of *mẹ*: **mee?, *ma?, *ʔmee?* and the reconstructed form **[ʔ]bo?*, which changed to *vợ* ‘wife’ in modern Vietnamese (Shorto 2006). To enable a comparison among the other branches of Mon-Khmer languages, the following table presents the reconstructed results for ‘mother’:

Table 1 The reconstructed forms of ‘mother’ in other Proto-Mon Khmer branches and in Mon Khmer languages (Source: MKED).

Proto West-Bahnaric	<i>*mee?</i>
Proto South-Bahnaric	<i>*me:</i>
Proto Central-Bahnaric	<i>*me:ʔ</i>
Proto Bahnaric	<i>*me:iʔ</i>
Proto Katuic	<i>*ʔamee?</i>
Proto Khmuic	<i>*maʔ</i>
Proto Vietic	<i>*me:ʔ ~ me:ʔ</i>
Khmu	<i>maʔ</i>
Bahnah	<i>maa, meʔ</i>
Mnong	<i>ma:j</i>

Stieng	<i>mej; me:i</i>
Old Khmer	<i>me, 'me, ame</i>
Khmer	<i>mae</i>
Chứt/Rục/Sách	<i>m^əɛ̃</i>
Maleng	<i>mê:ʔ</i>
Pong	<i>me:</i>
Mường	<i>me:⁴⁶</i>

Regarding the similarity of these word forms in Vietnamese and Tai languages, in Proto Tai, the reconstructed form of mother is **me:^B*, and in some other Tai dialects, *me:^{B2}*, *me:^{B2}*, and *me^{B2}* (Pittayaporn 2009). This is probably the why Alves (2017) claimed that there was not enough evidence to confirm the origin of the term *mẹ*. Other scholars such as Ly Tung Hieu (2015) even asserted that both *mẹ* and *bố* originated from a Tai language ('Tày' language as he wrote).

However, the term *mẹ* together with two other terms *mệ* all have phonetic forms that are more related to those reconstructed forms mentioned in Table 1. Thus, if *mẹ* was identified as a Tai loanword, this implies the possibility that not only Vietic languages but also other Mon-Khmer languages borrowed the term 'mother' *mẹ/mệ* from Tai languages. These conditions are unlikely to have occurred. Moreover, it is worth noting that in the Mường language, the term to refer to 'mother' is *mế*.¹ With regard to the tonal and vowel correspondences, the reciprocal between /e/ in *mệ* and /ɛ/ in *mẹ*, between 'sắc' tone in *mế* and 'nặng' tone in *mệ* further support the idea that *mệ* and *mế* as well as *mệ* and *mẹ* originated from the same source and that they can all be identified as Austroasiatic terms.

Meanwhile, the term *mạ* has a clear phonetic relationship with the reconstructed form **maʔ* in Proto-Mon Khmer. Moreover, in terms of geographical distribution, *mạ* (as well as *mệ*) is still used in Central dialects (Map 1). As analyzed and indicated in my previous study (Trần Thị Hồng Hạnh 2023), some kinship terms in Central dialects such as *o* (aunt) and *ả* (sister) can be identified as terms of Proto-Austroasiatic origination based on historical evidence of phonetic correspondence (Table 2).

¹ I use this spelling according to the spelling in *Đẻ đất đẻ nước* (The Muong Epics of 'The Birth of the Earth and Water') (Đặng Văn Lung 1988). This is also the spelling whose use is quite popular in newspapers. In the Mường - Việt Dictionary (Nguyễn Văn Khang 2002), the spelling is *mế*.

Map 1 Terms for ‘mother’ in Northern and Central dialects.

Table 2 Correspondences between *o*, *â*, and Proto-Austroasiatic/Austroasiatic forms.

<i>Terms</i>	<i>Proto-Austroasiatic/Austroasiatic forms related</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
<i>o</i> ‘father’s sister’	Proto Mon-Khmer: *ʔɔh	younger sibling
	Proto Mon-Khmer: *ʔ[o]ʔ	elder sibling
	Proto Vietic: *ʔɔ: Chứt, Malieng, Tho: ʔɔ: ¹	father’s younger sister
<i>â</i> ‘sister’	Chứt (Arem, Sách, Rục): ʔa:	father’s elder brother’s wife, father or mother’s elder sister

Based on the above arguments, versus the possibility that *mẹ* is a Tai loanword, I was inclined to suggest that *mẹ* as well as *mệ*, and *mạ* are terms of Austroasiatic origin.

2.2. The case of *má*

The source of *mẹ* was left open by Alves, but he did note that there were comparable forms in both Austroasiatic and Tai-Kadai. Meanwhile, the source of *má* is also difficult to assume because comparable forms could be found in both Austroasiatic and Chinese dialects.

Regarding the possibility that *má* is Austroasiatic in origin, an issue that emerges from the correspondence between *má* and *mạ* is whether it can be considered to be essentially the same as the correspondence between *mệ* and *mẹ*. In other words, a possible explanation for this correspondence is that *má* and *mạ* were also originally related. In this case, *mạ* is likely to be more ancient than *má* because it is more likely that **maʔ* in Proto-Mon Khmer changed into *mạ* rather than *má*, and, as noted above, *mạ* is used in Central dialects that are mainly agreed to be dialects that have preserved many of the original elements of Vietnamese language. It can therefore be assumed that *má* was a variation of *mạ* as the term spread southward.

Nevertheless, the distribution of this term seems to provide further support for the hypothesis that *má* is the result of the later Chinese–Vietnamese language contact. Southern Vietnam has a number of speakers of Chinese dialects such as Cantonese, Teochew, Hakka, Hokkien, and Hainanese who have been migrating to this region since the 17th century. In Cantonese, mother 妈妈 is pronounced as /ma²¹ ma³⁵/. In Teochew dialect, mother is 阿嫲 /a³³ ma³⁵/ and father is 阿爹 /a³³ tia³³/. Thus, this vowel and tonal correspondence indicates the possibility that *tía*, *má* in Southern Vietnamese dialects originated from these dialects. In terms of geography, *má* in the pair of *ba má*, *tía má* (father and mother) only appear in the Southern dialect. It can therefore be assumed that the term *má* was the term that appeared along with the wave of Chinese immigrants to Vietnam.

Map 2 Geographical distribution of *má* in Southern dialects.

Another piece of evidence that can further support this explanation is the fact that in the dictionary *Đại Nam quốc âm tự vị* (*Dictionnaire Annamite* 大南國音字彙) published in 1895, the entry for ‘má’ is explained: ‘*n. Hai miếng thịt ở hai bên mặt; mẹ, (kêu theo tiếng Khách)*’ (Nôm word. two pieces of meat on either side of the face; mother (called by Hakka language)).

Fig. 1 The entry for ‘má’ in *Đại Nam quốc âm tự vị*.

A. de Rhodes’ dictionary (1651) and Taberd’s *Dictionarium Anamitico Latinum* (1838) contain no entry for *má* with the meaning ‘mother’. The term referring to ‘mother’ in the first literary work written in *Chữ quốc ngữ* (national romanized Vietnamese script), *Thầy Lazaro Phiền* (The story of Lazaro Phiền) (Nguyễn Trọng Quản 1887), is *mẹ*. It was not until Ho Bieu Chanh’s literary works in the 1920s that the term *má* seemed to have just begun to appear. Therefore, the term *má* can be assumed to have appeared very late, around the end of the 19th century or the beginning of the 20th century.

However, Map 3 has important implications concerning which hypothesis on the diffusion of the term *má* appears to be stronger. If *má* had changed from *mạ*, the more ancient term preserved in the Central dialects, *má* (together with *mẹ*) must have spread to the South due to the Southern wave of Vietic residents moving southward around the beginning of the 17th century. This time period coincided with the first wave of the Hoa people² migrating to Vietnam. If so, there is no explanation for the fact that *má* did not diffuse to the North but only to the South and that *má* was first found only in documents at the end of the 19th century as analyzed above. This finding, although preliminary, suggests the possibility that *má* came from Chinese dialects.

² The Hoa people are the name Vietnamese people call Chinese groups like Cantonese, Teochew, Hakka, Hokkien, Hainanese, etc. who migrated to Vietnam at different times from the 16th century and later in the late Ming and early Qing dynasties, which seems to last until the first half of the 20th century.

Map 3 Geographical distribution of *má* in Southern dialects.

3. Conclusion

Based on an analysis of both historical phonetic evidence and the geographical distribution of the terms *má*, *mạ*, *mệ*, *mẹ*, this paper indicated that *mẹ*, *mệ*, *mạ* can be argued to be Austroasiatic etymons (*mẹ*, *mạ*, *mệ*), while cases of *má* are likely to be loanwords from Chinese dialects. These findings may help provide us with more understanding of the Vietnamese kinship terms, which are not only rich in number but also diverse in origin. However, further studies of Vietnamese kinship terms are called for that can provide more evidence of the proposed hypotheses of how those terms originated while also taking other terms into account.

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